

THE GREAT FIRE OF LONDON 2017- UK
 (The Grenfell Tower Fire)
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Introduction

In 2001 I retired from the City of London having held the post of Principle Building Control Officer. This is the first paper I have written which directly relates to my public employment profession. But with the news that the UK Government has passed an Act of Parliament called “The Building Safety Act 2022”, I need to respond to the event of the fire, which took 72 lives and was the worst residential fire in the UK since World War 2 – i.e. 77 years previously. This new Act is supposed to take full effect some time in 2023.

The Official Enquiry into the fire was completed in 2022. In this paper I will attempt to comment on reasons for the spread of the fire not fully covered in the Official Enquiry.

In this paper I will not closely examine the new Building Safety Act, but I will mention previous Building Acts, especially those which had their origins in the Great Fire of London in 1666. Yes it is true, that London had a great lesson about fire spread involving residential buildings, more than 350 years prior to the Grenfell Tower fire. Yet this disaster has been allowed to happen, and now we know there are more than 360 other tower blocks in England alone, which have the same potential risk; and I guess that world-wide

there may be thousands. The spread of this fire was building control gone very wrong. It is my hope that other nations will benefit from this paper with respect to the safety of the public from fire in their cities and in tall buildings.

Safety of building occupants was not only one aspect of my employment, it was also my passion. When I first saw the picture above on that fateful day, I wept bitterly for the lost lives; and I knew immediately that it was combustible cladding, wrongly applied to the building, which was the cause. Bad building control. Innocent people's lives taken through the incompetence of those who are supposed to protect them; this includes builders, architects, politicians, law makers and building control personnel.

Let's look closer at this tragedy and understand that it should never have happened.

Some Facts About the Grenfell Tower Fire

New cladding was added to the exterior of the building in 2016. This new cladding had a sandwich of two aluminium sheets with a central core of highly combustible polyethylene polymer. Competent building control officers know that aluminium alloy melts early on in a fire. (500°C), and fire soon breaks out of the windows in a full fire situation. The combination of these two facts about the nature of materials and the nature of fire should be part of the education of all building control officers. When the fire in any room breaks out of the window it will immediately attack any cladding fixed to the external wall surface. The air alone can be 1500°C. Flames may well be over 2000°C. It is for this reason all cladding must be of non-combustible material throughout, since fire may break through to any part which is combustible. Then the fire will spread over the external surface of the walls and subsequently into other rooms through their windows. This is what happened in the great Grenfell fire of 2017.

Fire has a great capacity to enter the smallest spaces; and to leap over any barrier to its flow. Polyethylene melts between 100°C and 150°C. Hence as soon as the aluminium has reached that temperature the fuel will start to flow out of the cladding panels. The Official Enquiry confirmed that it was the polyethylene cladding which was the main contributor to the fire spread across the walls of the Grenfell Tower. This was constructional madness, in my opinion.

A fire started in a flat on the 4th floor of Grenfell Tower just before 1.00 a.m. on 14th June 2017. A 999 emergency call was made to the fire brigade at 00.56 a.m. Within fifteen minutes the fire had broken out of the window behind the new cladding. Within another fifteen minutes (at 01.25), a 999 call was made to the fire brigade reporting a fire breaking into a flat on the 14th floor; 10 floors up the building. By 1.30, thirty four minutes after the first report, a 999 call was made to the fire brigade reporting a fire in a flat on the 22nd floor. That is 10 floors up in the first 15 minutes and another 8 floors up in the next 5 minutes. This was indeed a great fire. See the photo on page 19. At that time the fire was more than twice the height that the

fire brigade's water jets could reach.

The fire did not only spread vertically. It also spread horizontally around the sides of the building. Melting the aluminium sheets and exposing more fuel in the form of polyethylene to accelerate the fire. The fire was soon out of control, meaning the fire brigade had no hope of stopping the fire or the spread. I will not criticise the Fire Brigade in any way, as those on the Official Enquiry have done. The first fire engine arrived at 01.01 a.m. the fire fighters entered the kitchen where the fire was at 01.14. By

this time the fire was out of the window and well on its way to the 14th floor. This was an unprecedented situation of rapid fire spread. Such a fire had never occurred before in London. There was little or no training or prior knowledge of what to do in such a situation. In the circumstances they acted bravely and heroically to save many lives.

The Official Enquiry spent a lot of time going into all the details of the cladding, the fire brigade response, the local authority management of the building etc. etc. many items which are not relevant to this paper. My focus here is on the use of anything combustible on the outer surface of any building. I do not support all the excuses and technical reasons for using combustible materials in this situation, and if I had been in control of the Grenfell refurbishment I would not have allowed its use. That being the case the flat fire would have occurred, it may have broken out of the window to the kitchen; the fire brigade would have arrived and extinguished it. All the issues about whether the residents should "stay put" or whether the fire brigade response was appropriate, and the technicalities of the combustible cladding, its fire tests and the installation of it, would not have arisen. Hence these matters are for the Official Enquiry, not for this paper. However the main point which did not emerge from the Official Enquiry is that London had previously developed a building control system which would have prevented any form of combustible cladding on the exterior of a building, hence the rapid fire spread would not have happened. It was the removal of that previous control system which was at fault.

Above are some of the basic facts of the fire. Put here so that readers can appreciate some of the reasons for the Byelaws which had evolved from the lessons about fire. Those which inner Londoners had learned over several centuries before this tragic disaster. So now we will examine some of those lessons. Let's hope they will not be forgotten again.

The Great Fires of London

The 1666 fire of London was not the first of such fires, in the year 1212 a fire that started in the City of Southwark, south side of the river Thames, eventually spread to London Bridge and across the river into the City of London, several thousand lives were lost in 1212. After the 1212 fire, thatched roofs were banned in London, and would have been reported by the City Viewers (inspectors) instigated by Mayor Henry Fitzailwin in 1189. During the 1666 fire of London more than 1,300 houses were destroyed, 87 parish churches and several large public buildings; 80% of London. Yet the number of people reported to have lost their life was less than the lives lost in the Grenfell Tower fire 2017. So in one way we can say that the 2017 Grenfell Tower fire was another "**Great Fire of London**".

After the 1666 great fire, those that governed London were determined to prevent such an event from happening again. Also insurance companies saw the scope to sell policies to building owners, but this also gave them some obligation to fight fires. Hence private fire fighting organisations were formed and paid for by the insurance companies. At that time there was no fire fighting service provided by any public authority. Over more than a century many competing private fire brigades were eventually combined to

form the London Fire Engine Establishment (LFEE), which was privately financed by insurance companies.

It was not until nearly 100 years later in 1861 that the Tooley Street fire in the docklands instigated the first City run fire service; a publicly funded fire fighting service.

The Tooley Street fire mainly involved warehouses and their contents, forming a conflagration. Because it took two weeks to finally extinguish the fire, the LFEE implored the Secretary of State of the UK Government to take over the function of fire fighting as they were unable to continue to carry the responsibility. Also due to the fast expansion of London as a major port and thriving city, the fire risks were increasing. It was in 1866, two hundred years after the Great Fire of 1666 that the Metropolitan Fire Brigade Act came into force, giving birth to the Metropolitan Fire Brigade (MFB) in central London.

This shows us that when politicians take control of matters which affect the public at large, there can be a public safety benefit; but as we will see later on, the opposite can also be the case. Above is the early evolution of fire fighting in London, but what about the controlling Byelaws for the prevention and safety from fire in and around buildings?

The Evolution of London's Building Control

A simple analysis of how the 1666 Great Fire was able to spread so quickly and so far, showed that it was two main things which facilitated the spread. (1) The buildings were too close together and (2) they were made of wood. Although the streets were wide enough for horse and cart to pass at the lower level, the buildings overhung at the next floor level and became too close together. Also well seasoned wood is highly combustible, hence 17th century London was a fire disaster waiting to happen. It was these two main things which formed the heart of new regulations to prevent another Great Fire. Hence the 1667 London Rebuilding Act made provision for all buildings to be built of stone in place of wood, and for streets to become widened to prevent fire jumping across.

Another part of the new legislation required surveyors to be employed by the City of London Corporation to ensure that new buildings complied with the new provisions. This was a powerful provision for future safety of buildings within the London area. And was eventually to ensure the safety of all aspects of building construction in Inner London. An extract from the 1667 Act is shown below.

The Provision for Surveyors
(17th century spelling within the 1667 Act)

“And that the said irregular Buildings may be the better prevented or more effectually discovered. Be it further enacted by the Authoritie aforesaid That the Lord Maior Aldermen and Common Councill of the said Citty shall and may at their will and pleasure elect nominate and appoint one or more discreet and intelligent person or persons in the Art of Building to be the Surveyors or Supervisors to see the said Rules and Scantlings well and truely observed.”

(‘discreet’ in this context means – cautious, careful and judicious.)

These surveyors were later to become the famous District Surveyors with personal legal powers, under later enactments controlling London's taller, bigger and all buildings. This 1667 Act of Parliament was extended to the City of Westminster 40 years later. Soon after the great fire, many other British cities adopted similar building control laws.

An important part of the new 1667 legislation included not only compulsory brick or stone walls, but their thickness; which had to be not less than one brick (9 inches or 24 cm). Especially between adjacent buildings. This was called ‘The Party Wall’. This would prevent or retard the spread of fire horizontally from one building to another.

Why brick or stone? Timber is not only a combustible material, it also encourages fire to spread across its surface. Hence even before a timber wall is all aflame, the fire can

spread across the surface to another piece of timber nearby. So we have two issues to consider; the fire load (combustible material) and spread of fire (the type of surface). We will see below how these became important issues in the London Building Byelaws.

After the 1667 Act of Parliament more legislation was enacted to gradually include other matters such as drainage and foundations of buildings. Later the government of London was widened to what later became known as Inner London.

London is three cities in one, each with its own cathedral. (1) is the oldest part called the City of London – The Square Mile. (2) is the City of Westminster and (3) is the City of Southwark. On the map the yellow is Inner London, the orange is Outer London. Together they form what is now known as Greater London. The Borough of Chelsea and Kensington is the yellow area to the left and adjacent to (2) City of Westminster.

Prior to 1986 the areas of Inner London and Outer London had distinct building control systems. Inner London had retained the system described above with District Surveyors doing the building control. Outer London used the national system. Grenfell tower was built in 1974 under the control of the District Surveyor’s system. London as a whole was governed by the Greater London Council, known as the GLC.

What Was the District Surveyor’s System?

The act of parliament which gave the power to the District Surveyors was called “The London Building Act 1939” Previous similar Acts also gave this power but were mostly superseded by the 1939 Act; which was enforced by the Greater London Council (GLC) at the time the Grenfell Tower was constructed. Section 75 (1) of the 1939 Act states :-

75. For the purpose of aiding in the execution of the London Building Acts and any byelaws made in pursuance of those acts the Council may appoint any such number of duly qualified persons to the office of district surveyor as they think fit.

Section 76 restricts the persons who can hold the office of District Surveyor to those who hold a **certificate of proficiency**. This section (and section 78) allows those who have held the position of District Surveyor prior the 1939 Act to continue to hold that office.

Section 77 details the manner in which the examinations for the **certificate of proficiency** are carried out; and those who will be involved in deciding that a person has passed the exams and can later obtain the post of District Surveyor.

The legal requirement for examinations implies a legal duty or need to give training for appropriate officers to be capable of passing them. This is an important requirement in relation to the competency of those carrying out the function of building control. We can see that the provisions of Sections 75 to 77 above echo the 1667 provision. Thus it is clear that a robust system had developed since 1667 for ensuring that only those who were sufficiently competent and knowledgeable about all aspects of buildings, would be in control of their construction or alteration. This is the power of that original provision in the 1667 London Rebuilding Act – requiring “**discreet and intelligent persons**” to carry out the control. However, not all those appointed to assist the District Surveyor needed to have the **certificate of proficiency**. In 1975 I was appointed to be a District Surveyor’s assistant, and I can report that the application system and the interview by the District Surveyor ensured that those appointed were duly experienced to carry out the function of building control; including knowledge of the wide range of subjects which that entails.

All District Surveyors assistants were issued with a warrant which gave them power of access into any building at any time, if they considered that building work was going on requiring control and inspection. A power which neither the police nor the outer London building inspectors had in their hand. I had to use my warrant many times during the years I worked in inner London. Many building projects began without notice to the District Surveyor, hence we had to request entry or access to the building works.

The GLC was the central governing body of Greater London as a whole. Each London borough had its own administrative council. But common subjects such as roads, buses and underground were organised and controlled by the GLC in a huge complex of offices called County Hall in Lambeth, opposite the Westminster Houses of Parliament on the northern bank of the river Thames (see London map above).

Each inner London Borough had its own District Surveyor, some boroughs had more than one. These were organised and appointed through the central building control in County Hall. Although the vacancies for the post of District Surveyor were advertised nationally, in nearly all cases the post was filled from applications coming from Assistant District Surveyors (or Deputies) already employed by the GLC. All Assistant District Surveyors would hold the **certificate of proficiency** mentioned above. It is important for this paper to understand how a person obtained this certificate.

All GLC employees acting as assistants to any District Surveyor were invited to attend classes in several subjects. It was like going back to university but part time. I began to attend these classes after four years of working in Wandsworth for the District Surveyor. There were several subjects to study. Byelaws and legislation (English law), structural engineering, foundation engineering, architectural planning, means of escape from fire, dangerous structures and fire engineering. These were the main subjects. Experts in these subjects were the teachers, many of whom were District Surveyors. Success in these subjects would qualify a person to make an application for the **certificate of proficiency** examination. Very few were allowed to take this examination; and fewer passed it. I studied Civil Engineering at Kingston and also passed the very difficult examination to become a Chartered Structural Engineer; I can say that the process and examination leading to the **certificate of proficiency** to become a District Surveyor was much harder. This was the full application of the 1667 requirement - “**shall and may at their will and pleasure elect nominate and appoint one or more discreet and intelligent person or persons in the Art of Building to be the Surveyors or Supervisors**” This is what I meant above by the words “a robust system”.

The national system of building control did not have such a stringent requirement. Building Control Officers (BCOs) could be appointed to any local authority from any

person experienced and professionally qualified in one of the various building construction professions; Engineers, Architects or Surveyors, or someone with a degree in Building Control. Then, in time, they work their way up to becoming more senior. Hence those carrying out the role would become competent persons. But their legal powers of control were not the same the District Surveyors, given to them in the London Constructional Byelaws, under the 1939 London Building Act. One appropriate example below:-

Byelaw 6.15 :- External Cladding

1. External cladding to a building shall be of such materials, of such thickness and fixed and supported in such manner and in such sequence as the District Surveyor shall approve.

2. Sufficient permanently flexible joints shall be provided horizontally and vertically as approved by the District Surveyor to allow for differential movement in the cladding and in the structure to which it is attached.

3. Any metal dowels and fixings securing the cladding shall be of stainless steel, phosphor bronze or aluminium bronze alloy to the satisfaction of the District Surveyor.

Provided that

Other materials for dowels and fixings may be used if the District Surveyor is satisfied as to their suitability and permanency and that such dowels and fixings are adequately protected from corrosion.

There were many Byelaws similarly giving the sole power of discretion to the District Surveyor. Very few people appealed against these decisions.

In all these above requirements for cladding, the District Surveyor had to be satisfied. There is no mention of any documentation or British Standard or any other proof, only that the District Surveyor has to be satisfied. This kind of simple requirement did not exist in the National Building Regulations which were in force in the rest of England and Wales. Instead other published standards and documents were referred to as ways to comply with the regulations. These same standards and documents could be used to impress the District Surveyor, but finally it was his decision to allow a method and/or a material. This is a trained and experienced person, with legal powers, making the decisions, not a book.

From 1975 I had many things to learn, about what was allowed and what was not, under the London Building Byelaws. When I noticed a private house in a long terrace in Wandsworth being clad on the front wall with pretty timber boards, I asked the District Surveyor if it constituted building work. I was told it did and not only that, he said "We do not allow combustible coverings on the outside of a building, so it will have to come off." This is what in Byelaw 6.15 - 1. above "**as the District Surveyor shall approve.**" means in practise. A human being decides, not a book. If all houses in that terrace had timber wall cladding, then we may get back to the 1666 situation in respect of fire spread.

The national method required the interpretation of many more words and technical standards to be satisfied. And as we all know, the more words there are the more room there is for others to find ways of interpretation, with which they may prove their case. The Independent Review of Building Regulations and Fire Safety published in 2018 as a result of the Grenfell fire, has more than 60,000 words. Any one who can traverse the minefield of that document and know clearly what should be done, deserves a medal for doing so. Yet with all these words it does not recommend banning combustible cladding to buildings in all cases. Too many words and no appropriate result. This is the basic reason that the UK does not have a written constitution for its governance. Instead it is held in the minds, by custom and practice, by those whose job it is to see that we keep to it. Also as things change with time the constitution will evolve with it. More words

simply means many more different interpretations. Giving the District Surveyor the legal power to decide, averts argument and the possibility of lower standards. But of course that District Surveyor would need to be very experienced and knowledgeable in all matters of building construction; and in our case here, all knowledge about materials, fire and their characteristics. And this would arise because he had obtained the **certificate of proficiency**. This was the case only in Inner London. The decisions of the District Surveyor were highly regarded and rarely disputed. I worked for about 11 years within this District Surveyor system, and was in the process of training and study to obtain the **certificate of proficiency** when the GLC was abolished (see below). However, later I was appointed to be a Principle Building Control Officer in the City of London. So I came to know the difference between the old London system and the National System after I began to work with it. I soon learned that the national standards for some things were lower.

The Demise of the Famous District Surveyors

The first step towards the Grenfell Tower event happening, occurred in 1986 when Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher abolished the GLC and along with it the District Surveyors. We say that this is *"throwing the baby out with the bath water"*. Thatcher's political party were determined to reform local government, especially as many were run by a majority in her opposition party. The leader of the GLC at that time was Ken Livingstone. He was part of the opposition party to Margaret Thatcher. Ken had annoyed Thatcher by his way of running down her government. This made her more determined to abolish the GLC. This is not intelligent governance, it is simply bully-boy (bully-girl) tactics. It arises because local authority has been allowed to become political. Once upon a time local councillors were not elected on a party political basis but on personal merit.

When the abolition had been proposed, there was a large contingent of people who wanted the Inner London system of building control to be extended to the whole of England and Wales. I myself wrote a long letter to Michael Heseltine, the minister in charge of building regulations, laying out a strong case for the retention of the District Surveyors and the Byelaws. These pleas were ignored by politicians, who believed they knew better. Yet parts of the District Surveyor's system (not the national system) were transplanted to Hong Kong in the 1970s by the GLC at the request of the Hong Kong authorities, concerned about the safety in their many tall buildings being proposed for the city. Hong Kong was under British control at that time. Yet soon after 1986 one of the most important, vibrant, complex and populous cities in the world, had no central control of its affairs and had lost the above valuable system of building control. What was the logic of that? It was not long before a new London wide Council was needed.

I can state here with confidence, that if the centuries old system of the District Surveyors had remained in force, the Grenfell Tower renovation would not have been allowed to have any part of its cladding combustible. And the Grenfell Tower fire would not have extended to much more than one dwelling.

It is not my intention in any of the above statements to indicate that officers in the national system do not make competent decisions. I am sure they do in most cases; but it is not easy for them to know how it feels when there is more legal power supporting them, when the words in the Approved Documents are not clear or don't seem to be enough.

From what I have described above readers may agree that it was an act of political stupidity that Margaret Thatcher abolished the GLC and the established system of building control, which had been built up from the event 320 years previously. This was the system of carefully training and selecting **"discreet and intelligent persons"**. A valuable system of public protection was destroyed by the sweep of a politician's pen. As I implied on page 4 above, politicians can be a great asset to public safety, **OR** the opposite. The

abolition of the District Surveyor's system was such an act; opposite to public protection; and contributed to the Grenfell Tower fire spreading so fast.

The Approved Inspector System of Control

Some years before Margaret Thatcher abolished the District Surveyors and the GLC, her party was promoting a policy of privatisation of many once publically or state owned national functions. The postal system, and British Gas had already been privatised. In 1984 it was the turn of Building Control. The new system would allow individuals or companies to apply for registration as Approved Inspectors (AIs) to do Building Control. Their hope was this would eventually take away the function of control from local authorities. However it did not take off until 1997 many years after the Building Act 1984, which empowered the possibility of AIs to be appointed. This Act did not make any requirement for examination for AIs; or for AIs to give training to their employees.

The relevance of this to the Grenfell Tower fire relates to the effect on local authority building control. In the twenty years between 1997 and 2017 more and more AIs have arrived on the scene. There are currently (2022) approximately 86 Approved Inspectors in the UK. It was in 1998 that local authorities were allowed to charge for building control. Previously there was no charge. Some Approved Inspectors undercut the local authority charges and presented a strong financial competition to local authority control. This has forced the local authorities to become more financially efficient. Hence many authorities have had to reduce such things as training; with the view that they could spend a lot of time and money to train surveyors, then they may go and work for the opposition, viz AIs. The impact of this is that in many local authorities there is little or no formal training. This is in contrast to the system which had a legal requirement for training. Thereby putting highly trained District Surveyors and their assistants into the community to check on building works. Maybe the introduction of AIs was not so good in some ways.

The AIs cheaper rates and their willingness to be softer on regulations in order to obtain work, is another subject, maybe not relevant to this paper. There were no proper checks on the veracity of the way AIs passed individual building proposals. Also no formal examinations had to be passed so as to be appointed as an Approved Inspector. The Approved Inspector Regulations 2000, only required details of qualifications and experience to be presented prior to being appointed. No **"certificate of proficiency."**

Now we must move on to discover how the UK's National Control system compares with the Inner London system of the famous District Surveyors..

The UK's National Building Control System Compared to Inner London

The whole of England and Wales has a system of building regulations not quite as difficult to comply with as the District Surveyor's system described above. These National Regulations have their origins in what were called "The Model Byelaws" set up in 1875 under the Public Health Act of that year. These were a set of byelaw documents covering the main aspects of building construction control, drawn up by central government. At that time they were not mandatory, i.e. not legally enforceable. The modern Approved Documents are the same. They do not carry the same force of compulsion as Byelaws do.

It was always accepted that regional variations across Britain would have slightly different requirements for building control. For example, the soils, the weather, the customary materials, and building methods and styles would differ from region to region. In 1875 Local Authorities were encouraged to use the Model Byelaws and modify them or add to them any requirements which were thought to be suitable for their region. Then get them approved by the Local Government Board, creating a local system of building control. Some local authorities did not adopt any Byelaws.

These Model Byelaws reflected many of the requirements of the already established Byelaws in Inner London. Hence we can say that across the country building control was in some ways influenced by what had already been established in London for centuries. But there were no formal examinations in local authorities, hence no obligation to give training to building control personnel, however some did give formal training.

As time moved on the various regional sets of regulations across England and Wales were consolidated into a national system, The Building Regulations 1965. These were enforced throughout England and Wales including the Outer London boroughs but not Inner London, where the District Surveyors were in control until abolition in 1986.

The national system had a requirement for plans of the building work to be submitted to the local authority and work should not commence until the plans were duly passed. The District Surveyor's system also had the requirement for plans, but they did not need to be issued with an approval. Plans should be sent to the District Surveyor for his comments. This was part of my work for 11 years. Usually a list of helpful comments would be given to assist the architect and/or builder to do the work so that it would comply with the Byelaws. Any work proposed which showed non-compliance was noted and the architect and/or builder would be informed. Most architects, home owners and builders loved this system, because in contrast to the system in outer London and beyond, it was less bureaucratic and generally more helpful than the national system.

The National Building Regulations did not have a requirement anything like the process leading to the **certificate of proficiency**, of the District Surveyors system, for Senior Building Control Officers (SBCO) to be appointed. The legislation did not have such a requirement within it. Neither did the officers have a warrant for access into properties. Also the legal process of enforcement did not lie directly with the SBCO.

Building control officers would generally be required to belong to the Institute of Building Control (IBC). Not all inspectors, but senior officers would have a better chance of becoming appointed if they were members of that Institution. To become an IBC member the applicant would have to show evidence of a suitable educational attainment; a degree or diploma in building construction, along with experience in building construction. The applicant may also have to pass examinations set by the IBC. This way some control of the capability would be made. And we must never forget that all those experienced in building control would pass their knowledge and experience to younger members of their team. This way much training was given by handed down knowledge.

The legal power in the national system was invested in the Local Authority, the local council. Hence for an SBCO to bring about a prosecution where a contravention had occurred, s/he would need to get the local council's legal department to agree to take out a legal case. This may take time and may be a lengthy process; and may be refused. Legal people like to show that they are earning their money by looking into case law and precedents. This can take a long time while the building work is going on. Although SBCOs could issue a stop notice on building works.

The District Surveyors in Inner London were not part of the Local Authority. For example, I worked for the District Surveyor for Wandsworth. But he was not an employee of the Wandsworth Borough Council. It was the GLC who employed him. Also the District Surveyor could instigate legal action himself, without requesting permission from the his employer the GLC. I remember many situations where I had to serve a Notice of Irregularity and later instigate a prosecution where a builder had not complied with the Byelaws and refused to alter the offending work. Over the years many days were spent in the local magistrates court giving evidence in the cases. This was a far more effective means of speedy control of offenders. Also we were easily able to take legal action for

works carried out by the Local Authority. Not so easy for a Local Authority building inspector. Inner London builders knew that the person visiting their building site had the power to request legal action through his boss back at the office. This was a deterrent. It was not the same for those who administered the National Building Regulations.

In the amended UK National Building Regulations 1972 there were no restrictions or requirements for either the fire spread characteristics of external wall surfaces or insulation applied to external walls. Some restrictions were added in later regulations.

Above are the main relevant details showing the difference between the District Surveyor's and the national systems of building control. This reveals part of the reason as to how the Grenfell Tower cladding was allowed to be used, creating a fire spread which "*should never have happened*".

The Need for Building Insulation

A significant amendment to the National Building Regulations occurred in 1972, where the first mention of "conservation of fuel and power" was made. This naturally led on to a requirement to insulate buildings from heat loss. The Grenfell Tower, built in 1974, was in Inner London where the requirement for insulating new buildings had not become widespread by that time. Hence it was not constructed with an effective means of conserving heat within the dwellings. Many tall residential buildings across the UK were poorly insulated. It was not a traditional requirement when these were built; many in the 1960s, because the nation had not thought to keep the heat in, but to turn up the heating.

The higher you go the faster are the wind currents; this leads to the higher wind chill factor for tower blocks making it more costly to heat them and putting a higher demand on the nation's energy systems. The UK could not build power stations fast enough to meet the fast growing population (6 million more between 1950 and 1970 a 12% increase) and a subsequent fast increase in dwelling construction. Energy conservation became an important subject for new buildings. This later became a requirement for not only new but also existing buildings to be well insulated. Nowadays it is to do with CO² emissions.

For the above reasons the existing Grenfell Tower was insulated with external cladding panels, as described above. But at that time controlled by National Regulations.

Fire Tests

Fire test results can easily be worded in such a way that the reader cannot know of all the things that went wrong in the test, or all the conditions which were not included. It depends on which country the system is tested in and who does the test. Many UK tests are done in respected places such as the UK's Building Research Establishment (BRE); but often they are commissioned and paid for by a manufacturer, who calls all the shots about the test and the parameters included in the test report. The words in the test report may not cover all possibilities. The tests done at BRE on materials used on the Grenfell Tower walls, were not honestly carried out. The test rig was set up by the cladding company without the supervision of the BRE staff, hence supporting materials were used in the test which were not used in the construction. This is bordering on criminal behaviour.

When I worked in the City of London I went all over Europe to cladding factories to witness tests being done on pre-fabricated cladding units intended for buildings proposed in the City (the square mile). As a Principle Building Control officer I insisted that I witnessed tests myself, so that I could see everything that went on and could fully interpret the results report of the test. In those factories I could also inspect the cladding manufacture. Hence I was often dashing off to the City Airport for a visit overseas.

Although not directly related to cladding, I once went to a fire test in Sweden, where an innovative mist system was being proposed for putting out fires. The test was done

with a metal waste paper bin filled with a fire load and set on fire in a small test room. After the test I was not satisfied that it covered all real live situations. So I asked for the test to be done again, but placing the waste paper bin under a desk and putting more fire load in the bin. The fire mist nozzles were in the ceiling, so the bin would be protected by the desk. For me this was more realistic. The fire mist company were reluctant, so I said I would not accept the system unless they tested it in the way I had described. So they did it that way. The fire took longer to go out, but it did before the fire load had been all consumed in the fire. Everybody cheered when the flames were finally extinguished.

I give this example as another way of saying "*a human decides, not a book*" mentioned on page 7 above. For new products with which building control is not familiar, a fire test report is only words. If the building control officer was not present at the test s/he will not be able to interpret the text fully. Or ask for some relevant modification to the test procedure. As protection against fire is important, then all those involved must get personal close experience in relation to fire tests. Manufacturers are economic with the truth.

Even so there are many other issues even if a product has a good fire test result. When the panels on the Grenfell Tower were exposed to the fire, the polyethylene core would soon become a thin liquid and flow out, and add highly combustible fuel to the already raging fire. Even if the panel is a sealed metal box it will have creases or seams as part of its production method. Whatever metal it is made of, small openings can occur due to the action of the fire. This can happen before the metal melts, due to the metal box distorting and buckling under heat. Such a scenario might not be obvious in a BS 476 surface spread of flame fire test. If I had been witnessing such a test I would have asked for a hole to be made in the metal panel (steel or aluminium) so as to see what happened if any combustible contents of the panel were to emerge during the test.

This is the kind of logic and participation which was educated into all those who needed it in the District Surveyor's system, which was based on "*a human decides, not a book*". Such training not being normal in the UK National Building Control system, may leave the public at risk. The UK Government did not know enough about the District Surveyor's system when it was abolished. Hence we have such a scenario as the Grenfell Tower spread of fire. Here I repeat, "*which should never have happened*".

We need to upgrade the education, training and examination of all building control front line personnel. Including updating on new systems, materials and products. If we do that then we may slowly get back to the unsurpassed control system which inner Londoners enjoyed, before it was mercilessly abolished by ignorant politicians. Now we need to examine the contribution to the fire spread made by the UK National Regulations.

The Contribution of the National Building Regulations

The first stage of the government enquiry into the Grenfell Tower fire was conducted by a retired judge, Sir Martin Moore-Bick. One of his statements near or at the end of the enquiry was, "*The rapid spread of the fire across Grenfell Tower remained profoundly shocking.*" And further ruled that the 2014-16 refurbishment of the tower breached building regulations. These would be the National Building Regulations. Perhaps from the information I have given so far readers will understand how the fire spread became so rapid.

This breach may well have been true; it may not be. We need not necessarily place all the blame for the rapid fire spread entirely on those who carried out the cladding work. We need also to examine how were they allowed to do it the way they did. Such large works of over-cladding existing tall buildings cannot be done without building control. As we have seen above, good building control depends on two main elements ; **(1)** the appointment and training of suitable persons and **(2)** the wording of the regulations which allow those persons to carry out the control. The Inner London system was long gone.

(1) Appointment, training and qualifications of building control officers:-

In the Building Act 1984 there is no section with a requirement for the qualification or training of those persons who carry out building control. Yet section 16(9) and Section 17(1) of that Act allow for an approved person to be allowed to certify that plans do comply with the regulations. No qualifications or proof of training is mentioned as a requirement for such a person to be able to give such a certificate. The Local Authority have no power to reject such certified plans. Which presumably means the work also cannot be rejected, even if it does not comply with the regulations. This method of approval has to be covered by insurance. This weakens the whole purpose of regulation.

In 2006, following the appointment of several Approved Inspectors to do building control, the UK government issued a document called "Building Control Performance Standards." This came about because as it says in that document:-

"Competition between local authorities and approved inspectors ---- provides a stimulus to greater efficiency and higher standards ---"

It does not identify how this would come about. The efficacy of that statement is in doubt. It goes on to say:-

"--- However, these same market forces also have the potential to drive down building control standards. Thereby threatening the health and safety of building users. ----"

It is mostly the administrative aspects of building control which are mentioned in that document, relating to passing of plans and inspection of building works. Educational and prior training of officers to do these things are not mentioned other than a two line requirement :-

The Building Control Body shall ensure that suitable arrangements exist for Continuing Professional Development and in-service training of its technical staff.

This is not a legal requirement, hence it is nowhere equivalent to the Inner London requirement for senior officers to be examined and pass the "**certificate of proficiency**".

(2) The wording of the regulations :-

At the beginning of Approved Document B (Fire Safety) it states :-

"The Approved Documents are intended to provide guidance for some of the more common building situations. However, there may well be alternative ways of achieving compliance with the requirements. "

"Thus there is no obligation to adopt any particular solution contained in an Approved Document if you prefer to meet the relevant requirement in some other way."

This statement undermines the authority of all the technical requirements and of the building control personnel right from the beginning. In this case all the fire safety matters.

If the combustible cladding was given approval by the building controllers, then how can we blame the builders? If the regulations were not clear enough that combustible material should never be used on external walls in any circumstances, then how can we blame the building control authority? Hence the statement above made by Sir Martin Moore-Bick may not be true if the Government had not given clear enough guidelines in the first place. This is the focal point for me. If it is written words which control the fire spread precautions and not a human being, we cannot expect those words to contain all the knowledge and experience of a person who has, for many years, studied and practiced the art of building control. Because politicians and law makers do not understand all the factors involved. This remains the case however much they may consult experts.

It is my experience that builders and developers will always attempt to save money on the cost of building materials. This they will do in a variety of ways. They will propose to use cheaper materials, which they know do not comply with regulations, in the hope that an inexperienced control officer will not notice. If they get approval for the material then it will not be the builder or developer who is at fault if a later problem arises. Or they will get approval for material which does comply with the regulations, but when the work is carried out they will change their plans and use a similar cheaper material; again in the hope that an inspector will not notice. Again this is bordering on criminal behaviour. But few builders have been treated as criminals for bad building work. However, the London police are considering to do this after the Grenfell public enquiry has been completed and published its findings. And it may include building controllers.

Therefore to avoid any fire risk to cladding, three things are important :- (A) clear wording of regulations with a good approval system. (B) Sufficient site inspections to ensure that the approved materials are deployed correctly throughout the building works. And (C) the power of discretion given to a highly competent and trained control surveyor. The building control officer for the Grenfell Tower only visited once per month. Nice diagrams and fancy words on architects plans are not buildings. Regulations, however many, and plans to comply with their meaning, may not produce a building with no fire risk. This was proved the case with the Grenfell Tower. Sufficient inspections are needed.

The wording in the previous relevant National Building Regulations Part B4 regarding external insulation cladding to buildings reads. (a recommendation only - not law)

13.7 The external envelope of a building should not provide a medium for fire spread if it is likely to be a risk to health or safety. The use of combustible materials for cladding framework, or of combustible thermal insulation as an overcladding or in ventilated cavities, may present such a risk in tall buildings, even though the provisions for external surfaces in Diagram 40 may have been satisfied.

The relevant part of diagram 40 shows three surfaces in different shades: White, dark grey and light grey. These three shades are described thus :-

- | | |
|---|---|
| | no provision in respect of the boundaries indicated |
| | class O |
| | Index (I) not more than 20.
Timber cladding at least 9mm thick is also acceptable
(The index (I) relates to tests Specified in BS 476 part 6) |

The above would apply to Grenfell Tower.

The tests in BS 476 part 6 relate to propagation of fire, not the combustibility of the material. Surface spread of fire is the subject of BS 476 part 7. As long as the building perimeter is 1m or more away from the boundary of the site, then these conditions apply. Class O is any non-combustible material or a material of limited combustibility. All the restrictions described relate to test to determine only the fire propagation and surface spread of flame for the material, not combustibility. Combustible material is not banned.

Where clause number 13.7 above refers to the use of combustible materials for insulation it refers to insulation boards which are not enclosed in metal. Hence all these regulation requirements and restrictions are not so relevant to the cladding material used in the Grenfell Tower, which had a metal surface. As far as any building control officer is

concerned the polyethylene enclosed in a metal sandwich may meet the requirements because the surface of the cladding unit is metal and would have no spread of flame rating at all. Also being metal it can easily be considered to be non-combustible, as it stands.

As far as I am concerned the panels fitted to the Grenfell Tower met the above requirements of the building regulations, because the reference to combustible cladding material relates to the plain insulation sheets fixed to the building's outer wall. This kind of insulation is described in a UK Building Research Establishment Report dated 1994 and entitled "*Thermal Insulation : avoiding risks*". Under paragraph 3.17 of this BRE report the spread of fire in wall cavities is discussed. The relevant diagram 41 is reproduced below.

This diagram shows combustible cladding fixed directly to a wall surface and protected from the weather by outer cladding material possibly metal. It does not say that combustible cladding should not be used. Clause 3.17 (b) states:- "Install cavity barriers between cladding and the structural wall at compartment walls and floors, and at each floor level of residential buildings as required by building regulations. (fig 41) "

There is no mention of combustible cladding which is enclosed within a metal sandwich. And any person reading the BRE document would get the impression that the panels which did have metal facing and the insulation boards must be as good as the system described here.

Here combustible insulation cladding is definitely permitted. There is no ban on it.

This is what happens in the course of time. At one time the metal sandwich cladding panels did not exist or were not used on the external walls of buildings. Hence Approved Documents cannot include them unless the wording is updated. For this reason my statement above on page 7 is relevant "*a human being decides, not a book*". Because a human being who is expert in his/her profession would be able to make a relevant decision based on his/her knowledge and experience. A book has no such intelligence. Hence I included item (C) on page 14 above, "*the power of discretion*" which connects with the subject on page 7 above, of giving discretion to highly trained and experienced surveyors.

So it would appear that Judge Sir Martin Moore-Bick made his statement based on his own judgement, with the reading of the building regulations guided by other legal persons. Perhaps he thought that Approved Documents had the same force of law as Byelaws. It was not possible for him to understand the situation as I have portrayed it here, because he has no experience in building control. The same is also true of many Government ministers who deal with Building Regulations and Approved Documents.

My own view is :- the concept that it is sufficient to produce complex documents, which try to cover all situations to control building works, is the fault. Hence it falls into the lap of the Government to simply say that combustible material on the face of a building is not acceptable in any circumstances. As my District Surveyor said to me in 1976, in respect of the timber cladding fixed to a terraced house in Wandsworth (see page 7 above). "*We do not allow combustible coverings on the outside of a building.*"

The fire would not have spread so fast if there had been no combustible material on the external wall of the Grenfell tower. Much of the questioning during the Official Enquiry centred around the combustibility of the panels. Yet in addition the enquiry has

shown up serious failings in building control, fire testing and construction methods and personnel. It has also shown the failure of the UK government to prevent all combustible materials from being placed on the external walls of all buildings. The enquiry has also shown up the fact that, with all the regulation approved documents in place and theoretically a good building control also in place (the National System), that (a) wrong materials can still get used, (b) building work will not be adequately inspected. And (c) fire testing on materials cannot be trusted. Further below I have made a recommendation to avoid this in future.

Following the Grenfell Tower fire the UK government has issued revised Building Regulation Approved Documents in 2022. Part of the opening words on the first page of the fire safety Approved Document B (volume 1 dwellings) states :-

Main changes made by the 2022 amendments

The changes focus on the following fire safety provisions

- a. Ban on combustible materials in and on the external walls of buildings: etc. etc.

From this wording it would appear that the UK Government has admitted a deficiency in the previous Approved Documents; because a ban on combustible materials on external walls is new, making it one of the changes. Is this going back to the Great Fire of London - and the subsequent ban on timber walls? I think so. This is what I meant on page 3 about lessons learned - *"Let's hope they will not be forgotten again."*

The UK Government has also admitted, in a roundabout way, that the abolition of the Inner London building control system needs to be partly reversed. However, this does not mean that the District Surveyors will return. What will return is a watered down version of the test of competency (the **certificate of proficiency**). This new Building Safety Act 2022 will set up a register of all building control personnel including all those who carry out any function related to building control. The new Act will also set up a building inspector regulatory body. This will oversee the competence of all those engaged in building control, whether Local Authority or the private sector. All such persons will be required to register under the new Act of Parliament in order to carry on in their profession. The regulatory body may also test the competency of those on the register. Registration will only last for a few years (maybe 5), perhaps requiring proof that the person wishing to re-register has kept up-to-date with the changes in regulations and the technology of building methods and materials. The grounds for all these things are laid out in the 2022 Act, the details have not yet been declared. How many will pass the test of this I wonder? And will it really produce better control of buildings? I think not.

Many people may pick holes in my simplistic approach above. I have not engaged all the technical and scientific matters which are raised here. This is to keep the case simple - i.e. that combustible materials should not be used on the face of any building. Even if evacuation is easy and no lives may be lost, it has the potential to cause disruption and economic loss to individuals and the nation as whole. Hence it should be banned.

This closes my case on the Grenfell Tower fire. Only to repeat, I knew on the day I saw the picture on page 1 above, that it was combustible cladding on the face of the walls which was the cause of the fire spreading, and I can add to that; I also knew it was a failure of Approved Documents issued by the UK Government; because I also knew that there was no real control of combustible cladding on the external face of buildings.

UK building control Approved Documents are only advisory. They are not law. They are also confusing in that they say building work which meets all the requirements in the Approved Documents may not necessarily comply with the Building Regulations. The equivalent in the District Surveyor's system, the Byelaws, were obligatory law.

Summary

The official enquiry in the Grenfell Tower fire was very thorough. Many will say that it left no stone unturned. But my view is not like that. The negative role of UK government interference in building control in the 20th century has not all been exposed. Politicians do not either know about building control nor understand the significance of the role which fire places in every aspect of the control of buildings. No one can easily predict where a fire will occur or what will contribute to its fast spread. It depends so much on human behaviour and the many risks which exist in all buildings.

When I worked in Wandsworth for the GLC, there was a very severe fire in one of the flats in a tower block in the borough. I had to inspect the structure and report on the viability of the columns in case the building might not be structurally safe. The heat was so intense that an old lady in the flat opposite could not escape and she was burnt to ashes in her own flat. It was a mystery how the fire was so intense and had spread so quickly. No one predicts such a thing in a dwelling. Hence the building was not designed for it.

The fire occurred at a time when there was a severe shortage of petrol. The fire brigade investigation showed that the occupant in the flat where the fire started had been storing petrol there. This fuelled the fire and contributed to the intensity. How could a building designer, or controller, predict or design for a factor such as that?

But the Grenfell fire is not so much about predictability. It is about the ability of building control officers to effect suitable control. This ability is given to them by two important matters. The first is their knowledge, training and experience; the second is the clarity, power and force of the law which supports them. In this paper I wished to point out that in London there was once a system which gave the best it could of these two things - education and legal power. Building control officers who do not have legal authority may find it difficult to assert control. There are few people such as myself who are still alive and can know how different it was when a powerful tiger of a control system was replaced by a tiger with no claws or teeth, 36 years ago. They may look the same from the outside, the difference shows itself when they try to exert their power. It is the involvement of politicians which has either given these claws and teeth or taken them away. This is why I have decided to make a recommendation, which may or may not be at variance to that already given by others. It appears to me that those on the Official Enquiry had no experience of the past system which was abolished in 1986. Or they had conveniently forgotten it. Before I leave this world it is my duty to present this paper.

Recommendation

The Official Enquiry has shown that all the organisations involved in building control, fire testing and certification of building products, have shown incompetence and lack of knowledge of the real issues. This includes the central government department in charge of building regulations. This is a major success of the Official Enquiry. Some of us knew this long before the fire or the enquiry.

It would seem from the Official Enquiry evidence, that most organisations involved in building construction are sleep walking their way through the control of both simple and complex construction of buildings, in every use class and every size. They are not paying proper attention to the vital details which affect the health and safety of the public.

The above is a major failure of the duty of care for those organisations at fault.

I have one final recommendation in relation to this subject and it relates to all other failures of building regulations and organisations to effect proper building control.

This recommendation is :- to take the whole subject of building control and regulations away from the Government, who it is that do not understand it and are incapable of getting it right. But this is not de-regulation. The District Surveyor's system handed the control of buildings to those who knew everything about the subject. This it did by giving the power to control, by being personally satisfied, into the hands of those who knew intimately the construction industry, and had satisfied a selection system through the **certificate of proficiency** so as to merit their post in society.

Compare the Approved Document complexity, which has technical and scientific matters referred to in relation to the use of cladding to the exterior of buildings, with the simple Byelaw 6.15 reproduced on page 7 above. To effect that Byelaw a competent person would have studied all the latest innovation and fire test information etc. etc. These s/he would use these in decision making. Thus the choice "to his satisfaction" would include all these and would be more up to date than a document produced some years before. Less words can be more powerful, giving less room for error.

Pass a simple law which sets up a single building control national body (BCNB) with the power to make simple Byelaws (not recommendations) as they see fit in relation to all matters to do with buildings including the occupation and the occupancy of buildings. Handing the power of choices to experienced officers. This body alone will have the sole power to control products, builders and professionals in the construction industry, and to prosecute those who fail to comply with their Byelaws. The BCNB should create a panel to be made up of existing and past senior building control personnel, who should be subject to a similar selection process as the **certificate of proficiency** described above. It can include retired officers involved in the subject. Also those in fire fighting and health and safety functions should have some input.

The BCNB should devise an appropriate **certificate of proficiency** and an examination for all those on the panel and those involved in administering the Byelaws.

This is giving control into the hands of those whose life is devoted to public health and safety and is the best way to get it right. All should make a formal promise to carry out their function. They need to be people devoted to the safety of their fellow citizens. With personal legal powers they will get a better sense of the importance of their role, in the same way police officers do. How many police officers could say that a single decision of theirs would have saved 72 (or more) lives? Building control is that important.

The BCNB panel should meet at regular intervals each year to discuss failures in buildings, new products and innovations that have been introduced into the construction industry; and the need for new or amended Byelaws.

The Byelaws produce by the BCNB should have legal status and not simply be guidance. Failure to meet the requirements of their Byelaws either with proposals or in the act of carrying them out, will attract prosecutions and fines and in serious cases prison sentences. They should have the legal power to modify or create new regulations. A building control system without legal rules and officers without legal powers is like a tiger without claws or teeth.

An independent professional body, possibly the Royal Institute of British Architects is needed to oversee those on the BCNB panel.

Epilogue

This epilogue is required in relation to those who perished in the Grenfell Tower fire. On page 1 there is a statement that 72 people lost their lives in the fire. This number is most likely not the correct number. But we need to remember all of them, even if we do not know their names or how many. Those who lost their lives were not killed by the heat of the fire. So it is unlikely that they suffered the painful fate of burning to death. That which killed them was the smoke. Smoke travels far from the fire and faster; and most people who die in a fire die from asphyxiation. Also their bodies were not burned in the fire either, they were cremated. Very little of their remains were ever found.

the funeral pyre

When the building had cooled down the search was on to discover any remains of the victims. But we all know that the ashes of a loved one after cremation do not resemble any part of a human body. Yet the authorities had to come up with a number for the media. Hence many tons of ash were picked through; some bone fragments were found and teeth. Then the scientists were involved to try and match DNA etc. to give names and a number to the victims. This process continued until a number was eventually published. However there are many reasons why we will never know the true number of those who perished on that shocking day in the history of England.

the ashes

I worked in building control in inner London boroughs for 40 years. This position gave me access to the inside of many hundreds of dwellings over those years. And I know at least two relevant facts about those dwellings. Many were seriously overcrowded; and some of those who lived there were not legally in the UK. In some buildings there could be six or eight people sleeping in a bedroom intended for two. Such was their situation of poverty that they had to share the £ rent between as many as possible so as to survive.

The Grenfell Tower was initially built as a Chelsea and Kensington owned residential block; so as to solve part of their housing shortage situation. But many years before the fire, the UK Government passed a law which allowed council tenants to purchase, at a very reduced price, the flat they were living in. Hence some flats in the Tower were owned by private landlords; and not subject to council rules relating to occupancy numbers. Hence it is known that there were many illegal immigrants in Grenfell Tower. Let's guess how many people were in occupation. There were 127 flats and 227 bedrooms in the block. Approximately 14 flats were privately owned. If 10% of the bedrooms were in an overcrowded situation then we may have 22 bedrooms with 6 people in and 205 with 1.5 people in. This would give us 440 people in the block. This is 150 more than the number published by the BBC as being in the building at the start of the fire. But I do not think my estimate is an unrealistic number, based on my experience of overcrowded residential properties in London. About 180 people evacuated the building and 65 were rescued by the fire brigade. Giving us 245 survivors in total. The initial number said to have perished was 72. This means that there were thought to be 317 people in the building. A little over the number published by the BBC. This means there may have been many more than 100 people unaccounted for, according to my estimate. Why this number? Because many of the flats rented from the Chelsea and Kensington council would also be over crowded, as they were rented by the legal immigrant community.

Why did they not evacuate with all those 180 who did? Either they were trapped, overcome with smoke or it was because they were not legally in the UK. Outside the building were police and many other officials. Some were afraid to come out and be counted; to be asked, “who are you?” “what is your name” etc. Previously these had known that they could normally exit the building and no one would ask them any questions. Now in the fire situation they thought the fire would eventually go out or be put out and they need not face the police or the officials. It is known many illegal immigrants did evacuate. But they quickly left the scene and could not be traced. The UK government announced an amnesty for them promising a speedy route to UK citizen status. But the number who remained and perished in the building will never be known.

My numbers may well be an over-estimate. I accept that. It is possibly in the higher range of the number of people in the block. There are other people who know this number better than me. Some may say some unknown victims had no right to be in the UK, but I say that they nonetheless did have a right to life. Even so we must remember and say a prayer for all those who died even if we do not know their names or how many.

God bless their souls.

References

The London Fire Brigade – The Great Fire of London
The London Fire Brigade – the Tooley Street Fire
Rebuilding of London Act 1666
The Public Health Act 1875
The Building Regulations 1965
London Building Acts -Byelaws 1979
The Building Act 1984
BRE Report 1994 – Thermal Insulation – avoiding risks.
The Building (Approved Inspectors etc.)regulations 2000
Approved Document B – Fire Safety 2000 edition.
Wikipedia – The Grenfell Tower.
Wikipedia – The Grenfell Tower enquiry
Various - Independent newspaper articles.
Building Control Performance Standards June 2006
The BBC – What happened in the Grenfell Tower fire.
Building A Safer Future- Independent Review - Dame Judith Hackitt - 2018
The Building Safety Act 2022
Relevant BBC Podcasts of the Official Grenfell Enquiry

As long as they remain available you can download the Official Enquiry BBC podcasts here – [BBC Radio - The Grenfell Tower Inquiry Podcast - Downloads](#)

END OF PAPER

Dr. Alan Wenham-Prosser CEng., FStructE (retired), MRICS (retired) DProf., MA

In case any reader wished to have more confidence in this paper I give some background to the education, training and experience received over more than 55 years.

Having left school in 1960 with only 5 GCE passes to recommend me, I was given a position in a structural engineer's practise in Westminster. The boss treated me like his own son and made sure I received all necessary training and education. This included a place on a part time course for the Ordinary National Certificate in engineering at Westminster Technical College. Duly passed in 1963. After a couple more years in the structural engineers office I decided I needed a fuller education in engineering. So I left working and with a council grant I went to full time education at Kingston Polytechnic College. During 3 years there I studied for a Diploma in Civil Engineering. Obtained in 1968. This enabled me to take the examination for membership of the Structural Engineer's Institution.

After that I worked in several engineering practises in the London area gaining considerable experience in all kinds of constructions. My first employment in local authority came in 1975 after beating 49 other applicants for the post at Surrey County Council, County Hall Kingston, to be the engineer for their proposed new County Hall to be constructed in Guildford. The project was eventually postponed due to cost. After which in 1976 I applied for a post in the District Surveyor's Service with the GLC. Just before the GLC was abolished I transferred to the District Surveyor's office in the City of London. Eventually aspiring to the position of Principle Building Control Officer. I was so good at dealing with clients, when the Approved Inspector system started I was made marketing manager for the City office, to try and get as many projects away from Approved Inspectors.

I retired from that position in 2001, but due to personal demand from developers, bankers and architects in the London area, I had to return to the building control profession. This was because my style of dealing with those clients, when working for the City of London, was very thorough and friendly. When working for the City, I would go to meetings in architects or developers offices to discuss new proposals, against the wishes of my superiors. Also I would get involved in methods to comply with the building regulations and advise them how they could achieve their creative aims legally. Hence they wanted me to deal with their rather complex projects in the City of London after I had left working there. After this request I went through the difficult process of registering as a sole Approved Inspector; the private sector building control system set up by the UK government.

For a person to be able to register as an Approved Inspector the Deputy Prime Minister's office had set up an application process. This required me to provide full evidence of experience in dealing with every issue connected with the control of buildings. This became a huge document. It was followed up by interviews where a panel of about eight experts in all these matters would confront the applicant and put numerous difficult questions on all the issues which might arise in the construction or alteration of buildings. I would say this was getting near to the process of testing a person for the **certificate of proficiency** to become a District Surveyor, but not as thorough. I satisfied this process and was appointed in February 2002. I called my company name - London District Surveyor.

Over approximately 15 years I acted as the sole person dealing with the building control for hundreds of projects all over the central London area; working within the Approved Inspector framework. With the exception that I employed the company called Green Door, to prepare a Disability Discrimination Act report for relevant projects. The demand for my service was overwhelming; yet I dealt efficiently with each project and made full inspections of all the work. Some of these were £multi-million projects which may have been otherwise dealt with by the City of London office from which I retired. Through my system described below, no stone was left unturned in respect of all the relevant building control issues for each project.

I developed a system called the Building Control Schedule, not used by any other building inspector (see appendix below). The schedule was regularly updated and sent to all professionals on the team. All those that dealt with me loved the system as it was so clear and gave them the full picture of the building control process. It also helped me to keep a check on each project and make sure all issues were dealt with at the plan approval stage and finally closed out prior to giving a final certificate for the project. Every job I dealt with was 100% completed. Thoroughness is my 'middle name'.

This above position consolidate my knowledge and experience of all building control issues. Hence I considered it appropriate to write this paper and pass some of that knowledge and experience to those across the globe who may find it valuable. Let's hope lives will not be lost so much in future if good building control is able to become developed around the world.

Appendix – Typical Building Control Schedule

In the building control schedule below the REG column contains the relevant number in the Approved Documents at the time of this project (2003). The ITEM column contains the specific clause reference which identifies the description in the REQUIREMENT column. AD= Approved Document. DDA = Disability Discrimination Act

QUEEN STREET PLACE - BUILDING CONTROL SCHEDULE - JOB No. AI-02-39 London District Surveyor . Alan Wenham-Prosser CEng., FStructE., MRICS

Schedule update log.					
10/07/03 Items B1-09, DDA-01, DDA-06, & DDA-017 transferred to tenant's package. Items AI-05, L2-06 & L2-07 added.					
23/09/03 Items M2-02, M2-07, M2-09, M3-03, DDA-11, DDA-13 updated. Items DDA-13 & DDA-16 removed (escalators).					
19/12/03 Items B1-01, B1-02, B1-11, B3-01, L2-01, L2-07, F1-02, H1-01, H3-01,, updated. B3-06 added.					
06/01/04 Item A1-05 updated and Item B3-07 added					
02/06/04 Items updated:- A1-03, B1-02, M2-10. : Items transferred to fit-out project:- B1-10, B3-04, B3-07, H6-01, M2-06, DDA-07, DDA-09, DDA-15, DDA-20. Items removed as not relevant :- B3-06, L2-06, DDA-12.					
28/07/04 Action items amended:- B2-02, B3-01, L2-03, DDA-18: Items updated :- A1-02, B1-02, B1-03, B1-04, B1-07, B2-01, B3-02,B3-03, B3-05, B4-01, F1-01, G1-03, K1-01, K5-01, L2-04, DDA-22 Item transferred to fit-out project:- DDA-08.					
31/08/04 Action items amended:- B1-05, B1-06, K1-01, M2-08, M2-10, Items updated:- AI-04, B1-08, B1-11, B3-05, H1-01, H3-01, J2-01, L2-01, L2-02, L2-05, L2-07, M2-10, DDA-05, DDA-10, DDA-14, DDA-19, DDA-21, Items transferred to fit-out:- B1-03,K5-01, L2-04, DDA-02, DDA-18, N2-01, Items removed as not relevant:- J1-01, J4-01, K3-01,					
ITEM	REG.	REQUIREMENT	DESCRIPTION of PROPOSAL	STATUS	Action
A1-01	A1(1a)	Overall structural design strategy to transmit all loads safely	Waterman Partnership design document.	Agreed	
A1-02	A1(1a)	Design of new lift lobby floor.	Optima calculations and details issued.	Agreed	
A1-03	A1(2)	BS 6399 part 1 1988	Floor loading of 3.5 + 1.0 KN/m ² for office areas.	Agreed	
AI-04	AI(2)	Stability of non-load bearing walls.	HRA Drawing A03/800/C1	Agreed	
A1-05	A1(2)	Adequate support for new cladding elements.	Areas of new cladding or over-cladding and internal stonework finishes.	Details required.	ISG
B1-01	B1	Adequate means of escape.	Occupancy ratios of 7 m ² /person for dealer floors and 10m ² /person for non-dealer floors. These may be increased if a phased evacuation system is deployed.	Agreed	
B1-02	B1	Fire alarm to BS 5839 Part 1	See separate alarm strategy document and MTT drg. E102	Agreed	

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B1-04	B1	Escape lighting required in large open plan areas and on escape routes.	MTT drgs. E200 -E207, E400-E418 and E300- E304.	Agreed	
B1-05	B1	Fire escape signs to BS 5499	Basic system of ceiling fitted signs proposed. See HRA drawings L12/098 to 105 (rev P02) + spec N15 (rev P1)	Agreed	
B1-06	B1	Illumination of escape signs	See HRA drawings L12/098 to 105 (rev P02) + spec N15 (rev P1)	Agreed	
B1-07	B1 DDA	A two-way communication system should be fitted in each of the disabled refuges in accordance with BS5588 Pt 8.	MTT drg. E106 + HRA outline spec.	Agreed	
B1-08	B1 DDA	Signage in accordance with BS 5588 Part 8 indicating "Refuge Keep Clear" should be fitted in the disabled refuge areas.	HRA drawing L02/120 etc.	Agreed	
B1-11	B1	Where ducts pass across staircase enclosures or escape routes, the duct to have fire dampers and fire cladding.	MTT drg. M307	Agreed	
B2-01	B2 (1)	Surface flame spread ratings to comply with Table 10 of AD B	HRA finishes schedule.	Agreed	
B2-02	B2(1)	Thermoplastic lighting diffusers to comply with Table 11 of AD B	None	Details required if proposed.	MTT
B3-01	B3(1)	Fire resistance period for structure required to be adequate. Includes all primary structure within the atria and the remainder of the building.	4 hour fire resistance to separation between NCP car-park and the office building. 1 hour period for the remainder of the building.	Agreed	
B3-02	B3(1)	Stability in fire of atrium lifts.	WP letter 04/06/04 + Notes on drg. SA/20/001/E01	Agreed	

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B3-03	B3(3)	Heat release from atrium space, required to be operated by the Fire Brigade when heat and/or smoke release are required from any of the atria.	Use of ETFE atrium roof with monitored trace wire roof opening system. HRA drg L12/105	Agreed	
B3-05	B3(4)	Fire stopping of vertical services ducts and voids. 1 hour period required from floor to floor.	HRA drgs. L12/100-105, 111, 112 & A08/001/	Agreed	
B4-01	B4(1)	The existing drencher system on the boundary with Walbrook Wharf shall be maintained to be effective for a minimum of 1 hour.	HRA Outline Spec. clause 2-6 + drgs. L03/102	Agreed	
C4-01	C4	Prevention of moisture entering the building through cladding and roof.	See HRA drawings A05/001, 003 to 008 (rev P01) + L03/153, 553 to 554, 655, 700 to 703 (all Rev P01) + Specs J31(rev P2) and J41(rev P1)	Agreed	
F1-01	F1	8 litres / Sec. for each occupant proposed	HRA outline Spec. clause 5.2.1	Agreed	
F1-02	F1	Adequate ventilation of toilet areas and kitchens.	See MTT Schematic drawing No. 4275/M102A	Agreed.	
G1-01	G1(1)	Adequate toilet provision.	Male and female toilets shown near each stair core	Agreed	
G1-02	G1(2)	Adequate washbasins provision	Washbasins proposed in all toilet areas	Agreed.	
G1 03	G1 (3)	Adequate hot and cold water	Hot and cold water indicated in all toilet areas.HRA Outline Spec. clause 5.2.10	Agreed.	
H1-01	H1(1)	Sanitary pipework and drainage to comply with the provisions in AD H with respect to pipe sizes and gradients, trap sizes , anti-siphonage, access for cleaning, materials, junctions and branches.	See MTT drawings P001 to P500	Agreed	
H3-01	H1 & H3	Foul water and rain water drainage to comply with requirements of H1 & H3	See MTT drawings P001-P500	Agreed	

ITEM	REG.	REQUIREMENT	DESCRIPTION of PROPOSAL	STATUS	Action
J2-01	J2	Safe discharge of flue pipes for generators.	In protected shaft see MTT drawings M 300- M309	Agreed	
J3-01	J3	Protection for building from the generator flue pipes	In protected shaft see MTT drawings M 300- M309	Agreed	
K1-01	K1	Safe design of all stairs ladders and ramps. Applies to ladders in basement and entrance stairs.	None	Details required	HRA (HOK)
K2-01	K2	Barriers etc. - as protection from falling.	None	Details required	ISG
L2-01	L2	New windows in existing frames to have U value of 1.2W/ m ² K, or whole building to have a CPR of not more than 20.4 kgC/m ² /year	ESRU Technical Report 191/04 issued 12/07/04. CPR of 13.4 attained.	Agreed	
L2-02	L2	Heating system to have separate energy metering with instructions / information to determine or maintain optimum energy consumption	See MTT drgs. E 100 and E101 tenants metering each floor.	Agreed	
L2-03	L2	Energy efficiency rating information of heating boilers.	None	Details required	ISG
L2-05	L2	Air conditioning system to be 10% more efficient than the previously installed system	Requirement met by virtue of the ESRU report. CPR of 13.4 attained.	Agreed	
L2-07	L2	New glazing with new frames to have a centre pane U-value of not less than 1.2W/m ² K. As an alternative the whole building to have a CPR of not more than 20.4 kgC/m ² /year.	ESRU Technical Report 191/04 issued 12/07/04 CPR of 13.4 attained.	Agreed	
M2-01	M2	The each leaf of the front entrance doors should allow a clear opening width of 800mm.	HRA plan L02/600 Rev P04	Agreed	
M2-02	M2	The toilet corridor at the rear of the reception should have a minimum clear width of 1200mm.	No worse than existing situation. Agreed under Part M.	Agreed on existing basis	

ITEM	REG.	REQUIREMENT	DESCRIPTION of PROPOSAL	STATUS	Action
M2-03	M2	All internal door leafs should allow a clear opening width of 750mm.	Internal doors agreed as indicated on HRA plans A06/001 (Rev P01). Fire exit doors awaited.	Agreed	HRA
M2-04	M2	A leading edge of 300mm should be provided to the lobby doors, adjacent the accessible WC's in core A on the 1st, 2 nd and 3 rd floors.	HRA plan L02/111 Rev P04	Agreed	
M2-05	M2 DDA	Vision panels should be fitted in the doors providing access into the WC and disabled refuge lobbies. The panels should allow a zone of visibility between 500mm and 1500mm from the floor.	Vision panels provided at 600-2000mm. Indicated on HRA plan A06/002 (Rev P1)	Agreed	
M2-07	M2	Handrails in accordance with diagram 5 in M2 should be fitted to both sides of the reception steps.	HRA plan A02/330 Rev P02	Agreed	
M2-08	M2	Contrasting nosing should be fitted to the reception/atrium steps.	None	Details required	HRA (HOK)
M2-09	M2	The reception steps should be designed in accordance with M2.	HRA plan A02/330 Rev P02.	Agreed	
M2-10	M2 DDA	The atrium and rear corridor lifts should be designed in accordance with Part M or BS 8300:2000	HRA Access Statement 06/08/04	Agreed	
M3-01	M3	The door providing access into the accessible toilet at the rear of the reception should open outwards.	Agreed. Indicated on plan L02/170 (Rev P01)	Agreed	
M3-02	M3 DDA	The lobbies providing access into the ground floor accessible toilets located in the offices should be designed in accordance with BS 8300:2001 having a length of 2496mm (1570mm + 926mm door)	Agreed, as indicated on plans L02/150 & 160 (rev P03)	Agreed	
M3-03	M3 DDA	The accessible toilets and fittings within should be designed in accordance with BS8300:2001	HRA spec. N13 Rev P2 and accompanying documents.	Agreed	
DDA-03	DDA	All fire doors should have self-closures that do not exert a pressure of greater than 30N. Self-closing devices fitted to door that are not fire doors should have a maximum pressure of not more than 20N.	Concealed door closure HRA details XX9124 Specification S01 agreed	Agreed	

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DDA-04	DDA	The floor finish in the accessible toilets should be slip resistance when wet and dry.	Ceramic matt tiles agreed. Specification – HRA spec M40 (Rev P2)	Agreed	
DDA-05	DDA	The walls should contrast in colour to the fittings provided within the accessible toilet facilities.	HRA drg. L10/112/C2 and HRA spec. K10:155 and N13:350	Agreed	
DDA-10	DDA	The door furniture fitted throughout should satisfy BS8300:2001	Allgoods hardware summary	Agreed	
DDA-11	DDA	All entrance matting should extend a minimum of 1500mm into the building from the entrance doors.	HRA plan L02/600 Rev P04	Agreed	
DDA-14	DDA	All signage should be designed and located in accordance with the Sign Design Guide, a guide to inclusive design. (see www.cae.org.uk)	HRA letter dated 06/08/04	Agreed	
DDA-19	DDA	The second set of doors en-route from the basement car park to the reception lift should be hung on the same side as the first set of doors.	HRA drg. L01/099/C07	Agreed	
DDA-21	DDA	The columns in the reception should contrast in colour from the floor finish.	HRA letter dated 06/08/04	Agreed	
DDA-22	DDA	The lighting within the building should be designed in accordance with BS8300: 2001 to prevent glare and pools of light and darkness.	Toilet lighting proposals approved. See fax from MTT dated 31 st March 2003.	Agreed	
N1-01	N1	The glazing provided in the doors, including adjacent side panels, internal walls, partitions and windows should comply with Section 1 of the Approved Document N	None	Details required	ISG
N4-01	N4	Safe cleaning of windows, and roof access plant for this purpose to be provided.	See HRA drawings L12/200 to 205 (rev P01)	Agreed	

DDA = Disability Discrimination Act